

A Closed-Form Cell-Size Rule for Uniform-Grid Collision Detection

Efe Deniz Bağlar

Department of Computer Engineering, Ege University, İzmir, Turkey
efedenizbaglar45@gmail.com

Abstract

Broad-phase collision detection for equal-radius particles is commonly performed with a uniform grid, whose performance hinges on a single parameter: the cell edge length ℓ . The per-frame cost is a U-shaped function of ℓ — a too-fine grid pays for cell traversal, a too-coarse grid pays for quadratic intra-cell pair tests — and the cost-minimising ℓ depends on how the particles are distributed in space. We show that this optimum admits a closed form. Writing the per-frame cost as a linear function of the cell count and of the sum of squared cell occupancies, and identifying the latter as a discrete Rényi-2 (collision) quantity, we derive the cost-optimal cell size as an explicit expression in two runtime-measurable cost coefficients and the correlation (Rényi-2) dimension of the instantaneous particle distribution. **Our contribution is this closed-form cell-size rule**, evaluated once per frame at negligible overhead and requiring no manual tuning, together with an empirical validation of the cost model it rests on. Across eight 2D and five 3D scenarios spanning distribution dimensions from compact, low-dimensional clusters to space-filling clouds, the rule selects a cell size within a few percent of a per-frame oracle; the ubiquitous $\ell = 2r$ default and a naive space-filling dimension assumption are several times slower on low-dimensional distributions, most severely in three dimensions — precisely the regime in which the correlation-dimension term of the rule is active.

1 Introduction

Broad-phase collision detection narrows the $O(N^2)$ set of candidate particle pairs down to a small superset of genuinely close pairs, which a narrow phase then tests exactly. For N equal-radius particles in a bounded domain, the uniform grid is the standard broad-phase structure: the domain is partitioned into cubic cells of edge length ℓ , each particle is binned into its cell, and only particles sharing a cell or a neighbouring cell are tested for overlap [Ericson, 2004, Green, 2010]. The grid is simple, cache-friendly, and builds in $O(N)$ time, which is why it underlies particle simulators across graphics, games, and computational physics.

Its performance, however, is governed entirely by the choice of ℓ . The per-frame cost is U-shaped: a small ℓ creates many cells and the cost of clearing and traversing them dominates, while a large ℓ places many particles in each cell and the quadratic number of intra-cell pair tests dominates. The cost-minimising ℓ sits between these extremes, and — this is the crux — its location depends not only on N and the domain size but on how the particles are arranged in space. A tight cluster, a thin filament, and a uniform cloud of the same N particles do not share an optimal cell size.

In practice ℓ is most often fixed once, typically to the particle diameter $2r$ [Ericson, 2004, Green, 2010]. This default is convenient and, for dense near-uniform distributions, not far from optimal; but for non-uniform or low-dimensional distributions, and especially in three dimensions, it can be many times slower than the best choice. Two families of less naive approaches exist. Probe-based schemes

evaluate a handful of candidate cell sizes at runtime and keep the cheapest, paying a recurring search overhead. Analytical schemes estimate a good cell size ahead of time from a statistical model of the system: Sigurgeirsson et al. [2001] derive scaling laws for the optimal cell size of a collision algorithm, and Krijgsman et al. [2014] give a recipe for the cell sizes of a *hierarchical* grid as a function of the particle-*radius* distribution. What is missing is a rule that selects the cell size of a single uniform grid in closed form, from the *instantaneous spatial distribution* of the particles, cheaply enough to be re-evaluated every frame.

This paper provides such a rule. We write the per-frame cost as $T(\ell) = c_0 + aM(\ell) + bS(\ell)$, where $M(\ell)$ is the cell count and $S(\ell) = \sum_i n_i^2$ is the sum of squared cell occupancies; the coefficients a and b are hardware constants recovered from timing measurements. The quantity $S(\ell)$ is, up to normalisation, the discrete Rényi-2 collision quantity of the occupancy distribution, and its scaling with ℓ is set by the *correlation dimension* D_2 — the Rényi-2 dimension of the particle cloud [Grassberger and Procaccia, 1983, Hentschel and Procaccia, 1983]. Minimising T then yields a closed-form optimal cell size ℓ^* as an explicit function of a , b , D_2 , and the current grid state. Because every quantity in the expression is measured for free during the frame it is applied to, the rule costs a few microseconds per frame and needs no parameter tuning.

We make three contributions. (i) We derive the closed-form optimal uniform-grid cell size and the balance principle it satisfies (Section 3). (ii) We give a per-frame runtime algorithm built on the rule, in two variants: one that assumes a space-filling distribution ($D_2 = d$) at zero extra cost, and one that measures D_2 from the live distribution with a small probe (Section 3). (iii) We validate the cost model and the rule empirically across 2D and 3D scenarios (Section 4).

We are deliberate about what we do and do not claim. We do *not* claim that re-selecting ℓ every frame substantially beats the best single fixed ℓ for a whole run — our measurements show that gap is small. The value of the rule is that it reaches a near-optimal cell size *automatically*, from measured quantities, with no tuning and no oracle, and remains robust where fixed heuristics fail: on clustered and low-dimensional distributions, and in three dimensions, where assuming a space-filling distribution misplaces ℓ badly.

2 Related Work

Uniform grids and the diameter heuristic. The uniform grid is a textbook broad-phase structure for equal-size objects [Ericson, 2004]. Green [2010] popularised a sort-based GPU implementation for particle systems that bins particles into a uniform grid and tests cell neighbourhoods; both set the cell size to roughly the particle diameter and hold it fixed. Ericson [2004] discusses the sensitivity of grid performance to the cell size but does not prescribe a way to choose it from the distribution.

Choosing the cell size. Sigurgeirsson et al. [2001] analyse the complexity of a cell-based collision algorithm for particles in a velocity field and derive scaling laws for its parameters under statistical assumptions on the particle field. Krijgsman et al. [2014] address contact detection for *polydisperse* systems, where particles have widely varying radii, and give an analytical recipe for the number of levels and the cell sizes of a hierarchical grid as a function of the radius distribution. Rydquist and Esmaily [2020] give an optimal $O(N)$ scheme for particle localisation and collision detection on unstructured grids. These methods determine grid parameters once, before or independently of the simulation, and key them to the distribution of particle *sizes* or to statistical assumptions about the field. Our rule differs in three ways: it targets a single (non-hierarchical) uniform grid for equal-radius particles; the quantity it keys on is the *spatial* structure of the cloud, captured by

Figure 1: A uniform grid for broad-phase collision detection. Particles are binned into cells of edge length ℓ . For the query particle (blue), only particles in the shaded neighbourhood of cells are tested for overlap; the red pair is a detected collision. A small ℓ multiplies cell-traversal work; a large ℓ multiplies the pair tests within each cell.

its correlation dimension; and it is a closed-form expression in measured runtime quantities, cheap enough to re-evaluate every frame.

Spatial hashing and hierarchies. When object sizes vary or memory is tight, the grid array is often replaced by a hash table [Teschner et al., 2003, Ihmsen et al., 2011] or extended into a hierarchy of grids [Eitz and Gu, 2007]. These techniques address the multi-scale *object-size* problem; they are orthogonal to the single-scale distribution-dependent cell-size problem studied here, and the closed-form analysis below could in principle inform the per-level cell sizes of such structures.

Benchmarking. Serpa and Rodrigues [2020] provide an open framework and a set of dynamic scenes for the standardised evaluation of broad-phase algorithms, and survey the main techniques. Our experimental design follows the same spirit, contrasting scenarios that hold the distribution near space-filling against scenarios that drive it onto low-dimensional structures.

The correlation dimension. The correlation dimension D_2 was introduced by Grassberger and Procaccia [1983] to characterise strange attractors and placed within the family of generalised (Rényi) dimensions by Hentschel and Procaccia [1983]. It measures how the probability of two points falling in the same cell scales with cell size. To our knowledge it has not previously been connected to the performance of a spatial data structure; doing so is the conceptual core of this paper.

3 Method

3.1 Problem Setup and Cost Model

We consider N equal-radius particles (radius r) in a bounded d -dimensional domain ($d \in \{2, 3\}$) of volume V . Broad-phase collision detection uses a uniform grid of cubic cells of edge length ℓ ; $M(\ell) = V/\ell^d$ denotes the number of cells and n_i the number of particles in cell i . Each particle is binned into its cell, and overlap is tested only between particles sharing a cell or an adjacent cell. Figure 1 illustrates the structure: the grid, a set of binned particles, one colliding pair, and the cell neighbourhood searched for a query particle.

One frame’s grid-dependent work has three sources. *Insertion* of the N particles costs $O(N)$; since N is fixed this is independent of ℓ . *Per-cell* work — clearing the grid, the prefix sum over cells, and iterating cells in the query — is proportional to $M(\ell)$. *Pair tests* — the candidate overlap checks — are proportional to the number of ordered intra- and inter-cell candidate pairs, which is proportional to $S(\ell) = \sum_i n_i^2$. The per-frame cost is therefore

$$T(\ell) = c_0 + aM(\ell) + bS(\ell), \quad M(\ell) = \frac{V}{\ell^d}, \quad S(\ell) = \sum_i n_i^2, \quad (1)$$

where c_0 absorbs all ℓ -independent work, a is the per-cell cost, and b is the per-candidate-pair-test cost. The coefficients a and b are hardware constants; c_0 plays no role in minimisation over ℓ and is dropped from here on. The only modelling assumptions of (1) are that a and b are stable and that the cost is linear in M and S ; both are tested empirically in Section 4.

3.2 The Rényi-2 Entropy Identity

Let $p_i = n_i/N$ be the fraction of particles in cell i . The sum of squared occupancies is then

$$S(\ell) = \sum_i n_i^2 = N^2 \sum_i p_i^2 = N^2 e^{-H_2(\ell)}, \quad H_2(\ell) = -\log \sum_i p_i^2, \quad (2)$$

where H_2 is the discrete Rényi-2 entropy [Rényi, 1961] of the occupancy distribution. Equation (2) is exact: the pair-test cost is, up to the constant N^2 , the collision probability of the distribution discretised at resolution ℓ . By the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality $\sum_i n_i^2 \geq N^2/M(\ell)$, with equality if and only if the particles are spread uniformly over the cells; a uniform distribution thus maximises the entropy and minimises the pair-test cost at a fixed ℓ .

3.3 Correlation-Dimension Scaling

To minimise $T(\ell)$ we need the dependence of S on ℓ . Over a range of scales, the Rényi-2 partition function $\sum_i p_i^2(\ell)$ follows a power law, so that

$$S(\ell) \approx S(\ell_0) \left(\frac{\ell}{\ell_0} \right)^{D_2}, \quad D_2 = \lim_{\ell \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log \sum_i p_i^2(\ell)}{\log \ell}. \quad (3)$$

The exponent D_2 is the *correlation dimension* of the particle cloud — the Rényi-2 member of the generalised-dimension family [Grassberger and Procaccia, 1983, Hentschel and Procaccia, 1983]. For a space-filling distribution $D_2 = d$; for particles concentrated on a lower-dimensional set — a curve, a shell, a sheet, a filament — $D_2 < d$. This is the conceptual core of the method: the scaling of collision-detection cost with cell size is governed by the correlation dimension of the instantaneous particle distribution.

In practice $S(\ell)$ is only *locally* a power law. Its log–log slope $D_2(\ell)$ drifts slowly with scale, and the clean asymptote $D_2 \rightarrow d$ is approached only at large ℓ , outside the operating range of the algorithm. The quantity the rule below requires is the *local* exponent at the current cell size, not the global asymptotic dimension; our runtime estimator (Section 3.6) measures exactly this local slope, and Section 4 reports how far S departs from a single global power law.

3.4 Closed-Form Optimal Cell Size

Substituting $M(\ell) = V\ell^{-d}$ and the local power law (3) into (1) gives, with $K = S_{\text{cur}}/\ell_{\text{cur}}^{D_2}$,

$$T(\ell) = c_0 + aV\ell^{-d} + bK\ell^{D_2}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Anatomy of the per-frame cost (Eq. 1). The per-cell cost aM falls as ℓ^{-d} and the pair-test cost bS rises as ℓ^{D_2} ; their sum T is U-shaped. Drawn for a space-filling distribution ($D_2 = d$) of $N = 50,000$ particles in the 800×600 domain, using the cost coefficients fitted for the *stable* scenario (Table 1); the constant term c_0 is omitted. On log–log axes the two components are straight lines that, when $D_2 = d$, cross precisely at the closed-form optimum ℓ^* of Eq. (5), where the balance principle (6) holds.

Setting $dT/d\ell = 0$ yields the stationarity condition $d aV \ell^{-d-1} = D_2 bK \ell^{D_2-1}$. Solving for ℓ and expressing the result through the current-frame measured quantities $B_{\text{cur}} = a M_{\text{cur}}$ and $Q_{\text{cur}} = b S_{\text{cur}}$ gives the main result:

$$\ell^* = \ell_{\text{cur}} \left[\frac{d \cdot B_{\text{cur}}}{D_2 \cdot Q_{\text{cur}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{d+D_2}} \quad (5)$$

For $D_2 \geq 1$ the cost is strictly convex in ℓ , so ℓ^* of (5) is the unique minimiser. The rule has a direct reading: the optimal cell size is the current one, scaled by the $(d + D_2)$ -th root of the imbalance between the two cost terms. If per-cell work dominates (the grid is too fine) the bracket exceeds one and ℓ grows; if pair tests dominate (too coarse) it shrinks. At the optimum the two terms stand in a fixed ratio set by their scaling exponents,

$$d \cdot B(\ell^*) = D_2 \cdot Q(\ell^*), \quad (6)$$

the *balance principle*: the cost-optimal grid equates the per-cell and pair-test costs, each weighted by how fast it scales with ℓ . Figure 2 shows this anatomy: on log–log axes the two cost components are straight lines of slope $-d$ and D_2 , and for a space-filling distribution ($D_2 = d$) they cross exactly at ℓ^* , the minimiser of the U-shaped total.

3.5 Convergence

When the distribution is static, applying (5) repeatedly defines a map on ℓ . Working in $x = \log \ell$ and writing $s(x) = \log S(e^x)$, so that the local correlation dimension is $s'(x) = D_2(x)$, the map near

Algorithm 1 Per-frame closed-form cell-size rule

- 1: **state:** cell size ℓ_{cur} ; smoothed coefficients \hat{a}, \hat{b} ; smoothed dimension \hat{D}_2
- 2: measure $M_{\text{cur}} = V/\ell_{\text{cur}}^d$ and $S_{\text{cur}} = \sum_i n_i^2$ (free from the grid build)
- 3: update \hat{a}, \hat{b} from the per-region timers (exponential moving average)
- 4: **if** Mode B **and** probe is due **then**
- 5: bin particles at ℓ_{cur}/γ and $\ell_{\text{cur}}\gamma$; $\hat{D}_2 \leftarrow$ EMA of the log–log slope of S through the three sizes
- 6: **else**
- 7: $\hat{D}_2 \leftarrow d$ (Mode A)
- 8: **end if**
- 9: $B_{\text{cur}} \leftarrow \hat{a} M_{\text{cur}}$; $Q_{\text{cur}} \leftarrow \hat{b} S_{\text{cur}}$
- 10: $\ell^* \leftarrow \ell_{\text{cur}} [(d B_{\text{cur}})/(\hat{D}_2 Q_{\text{cur}})]^{1/(d+\hat{D}_2)}$
- 11: $\ell^* \leftarrow \text{clip}(\ell^*, 2r, \ell_{\text{max}})$
- 12: **if** $|\log(\ell^*/\ell_{\text{cur}})| > \varepsilon$ **then**
- 13: resize grid to ℓ^* ; $\ell_{\text{cur}} \leftarrow \ell^*$
- 14: **end if**

the optimum x^* contracts the error each step by a factor

$$c = \frac{|s''(x^*)|}{D_2^*(d + D_2^*)}. \quad (7)$$

If S follows an exact power law then $s'' = 0$ and $c = 0$: a single application lands on ℓ^* — indeed (5) was derived under that power law. When D_2 drifts with scale, $s'' \neq 0$ measures the drift and c stays well below one for the distributions of interest, so the rule converges in a few frames. The sign of the map is negative, so convergence proceeds by damped alternation. Under motion, if ℓ^* shifts by Δ per frame, the rule tracks it with a steady-state lag of order Δ — a one-frame delay, since the update can only target where the optimum just was.

3.6 The Runtime Algorithm

Algorithm 1 applies the rule once per frame, after the collision pass. The cell count M_{cur} and the occupancy sum S_{cur} are by-products of the grid build and cost nothing extra. The coefficients a and b are recovered online from per-region timers and smoothed with an exponential moving average. The optimal cell size follows from a single evaluation of (5); the grid is resized only when the change exceeds a small hysteresis threshold, which suppresses thrashing on noise.

The correlation dimension enters in one of two modes. *Mode A* assumes a space-filling distribution, $D_2 = d$, and adds no work at all. *Mode B* measures the local exponent: every few frames it bins the particles at two nearby cell sizes and takes the log–log slope of S through the three points, again smoothed with an exponential moving average. Mode B costs two extra $O(N)$ binning passes amortised over the probe interval. Both modes are far cheaper than a probe-based search over many candidate cell sizes, which must build the grid once per candidate. The cell size is clamped to $\ell \geq 2r$: below the particle diameter the power-law model breaks down and, with a one-ring neighbour stencil, $\ell \geq 2r$ is also required for correctness.

4 Experiments

We evaluate the closed-form rule on a benchmark of dynamic particle scenarios in two and three dimensions. The experiments address four questions: whether the linear cost model of Eq. (1) holds (Section 4.2); how much a per-frame cell size can improve on the best single fixed cell size at all (Section 4.3); how the rule compares against fixed heuristics, a probe-based search, and offline oracles (Section 4.4); and how much the correlation-dimension term contributes (Section 4.5).

4.1 Experimental Setup

Implementation. The simulator, the baselines, and the closed-form controller are one single-threaded C program,¹ compiled with `gcc -O2 -march=native` and run on an AMD Ryzen 5 5500U. The uniform grid is built with a counting sort; the occupancy sum $S = \sum_i n_i^2$ is accumulated incrementally during the count pass through the identity $(n + 1)^2 - n^2 = 2n + 1$, so that M and S are available every frame at no measurable cost.

Scenarios. The benchmark has eight 2D scenarios — *stable*, *collapse*, *explosion*, *vortex*, *funnel*, *pulse*, *multicluster*, *stream* — and five 3D scenarios — *stable*, *collapse*, *explosion*, *pulse*, *settling*. They are chosen to span the range of spatial distributions a grid must cope with: near-uniform clouds (*stable*, *collapse*), expanding and rotating flows (*explosion*, *vortex*), and strongly structured cases that drive the particles onto low-dimensional sets — *funnel* forms filaments, *multicluster* forms compact clusters, and *stream* forms channels. All particles have radius $r = 0.5$ and restitution $e = 0.95$, integrated at $dt = 1/60$. The 2D domain is 800×600 , run for 300 frames; the 3D domain is 200^3 , run for 60 frames, the shorter 3D runs reflecting the heavier per-frame cost of the larger domain. Each configuration is run with five random seeds at $N = 50K$, and additionally with three seeds at $N = 100K$ in 2D; we report the mean over seeds, with the per-seed spread quoted in the table captions.

Methods and references. We compare six methods. **Ericson** fixes $\ell = 2r$, the universal particle-diameter default [Ericson, 2004, Green, 2010]. **Density** fixes ℓ to the global-density estimate $(V/N)^{1/d}$. **Blind-9** is a probe-based search: every five frames it times nine candidate cell sizes in a geometric stencil around the current ℓ , each requiring a full grid build, and keeps the cheapest — the kind of runtime search the closed form is meant to replace. **Closed-A** and **Closed-B** are the rule of Eq. (5) in its two modes. Two non-realisable **oracles** bound the achievable cost: the *static oracle* is the single fixed ℓ that minimises the mean per-frame cost over the whole run, found by an offline sweep over roughly eight cell sizes bracketing the density estimate; the *per-frame oracle* instead picks, independently for every frame, the cheapest ℓ on that sweep. Every cost is reported as the ratio of mean per-frame detection time (broad phase plus narrow phase) to that of the per-frame oracle, so that 1.0 marks the per-frame lower bound.

Reading the oracle ratio. The per-frame oracle chooses the cheapest of several timed candidates each frame; choosing on noisy timings biases its reported cost slightly low — a winner’s curse, which for the median-of-three timing used here we bound at $\leq 2\%$. The methods and the static oracle are timed on the live simulator, whereas the per-frame oracle is timed by a separate, non-perturbing routine; the small difference in timing primitive adds to that margin. In practice a reported ratio

¹Source code and the full experimental harness are available at <https://github.com/kanemoda/closed-form-cell-size>.

Table 1: Cost-model fit $T = c_0 + aM + bS$ (Eq. 1) by ordinary least squares, 2D scenarios. The coefficients a and b vary little across scenarios, as expected of hardware constants; $R^2 \geq 0.99$ except on the two most violently dynamic scenarios.

Scenario	a (ns/cell)	b (ns/unit- S)	R^2
stable	7.93	10.85	0.998
collapse	7.87	10.13	0.997
explosion	8.60	13.99	0.992
vortex	8.27	8.36	0.992
funnel	8.01	12.06	0.994
pulse	7.68	9.80	0.878
multicluster	8.59	12.63	0.990
stream	7.46	9.48	0.926

within about 1–3% of 1.0 — and occasionally just below it — should therefore be read as *statistically indistinguishable from the per-frame oracle*. Where a bias-free comparison is needed we compare a method directly against the *static* oracle, which shares the same timing primitive.

4.2 Cost-Model Validation

The rule rests on the linear cost model $T = c_0 + aM + bS$ of Eq. (1), so we test that model directly. Sweeping the cell size over several representative frames yields a set of (M, S, T) samples, to which we fit a , b , and c_0 by ordinary least squares. Table 1 reports the fit for the 2D scenarios. The per-cell coefficient a stays within 7.5–8.6 ns and the per-pair-test coefficient b within 8.4–14.0 ns across all eight scenarios: they behave as the hardware constants the model assumes them to be, not as scenario-dependent quantities. The fit explains the timing well, with $R^2 \geq 0.99$ on six of the eight scenarios. The two exceptions are *pulse* (0.88) and *stream* (0.93) — the most violently time-varying scenarios — where the linear model leaves more variance unexplained; this is the honest signature of cache- and bandwidth-bound super-linear behaviour on the densest frames. It does not destabilise the rule, because only the ratio a/b enters Eq. (5) — the intercept c_0 cancels in the minimisation — and that ratio is well determined even when a few high- S frames inflate the absolute residual.

4.3 How Much Headroom Exists

Before comparing methods, we ask how much a per-frame-adaptive ℓ can, even in principle, beat the best single fixed ℓ — the *headroom*. We measure it by deriving both oracles from one shared frame-by-cell-size cost matrix timed with a single primitive, so that the two cannot diverge through a measurement inconsistency. As a control, feeding one frozen snapshot as every frame makes the two oracles agree to $0 \pm 1.2\%$, the timing-noise floor.

The headroom turns out to be small. On six of the eight 2D scenarios the per-frame oracle and the best fixed ℓ are indistinguishable within timing noise ($\pm 2\%$), at both $N = 8\text{K}$ and $N = 50\text{K}$. Only *funnel* shows a clear and repeatable benefit — +4.4% at 8K and +7.4% at 50K, as filament formation genuinely rewards re-tuning ℓ each frame — with *pulse* a modest second (+2.4% and +2.2%). We therefore make no claim that per-frame adaptation substantially beats a well-chosen fixed grid. The value of the rule, shown next, is different: it attains the performance of the best fixed ℓ *automatically*, from quantities measured for free, with no offline sweep and no tuning — and it stays robust on distributions where the fixed heuristics do not.

4.4 Main Comparison

Table 2 reports the comparison at $N = 50\text{K}$, with the 3D scenarios listed first because the effects are largest there.

In three dimensions the particle-diameter default is catastrophic: at $\ell = 2r$ the 200^3 domain is partitioned into 8×10^6 cells, almost all of them empty, and the per-cell cost dominates so heavily that Ericson runs 16–29 \times slower than the oracle. The density heuristic is far better — within 1% of the oracle on the near-uniform *stable* and *collapse* — but degrades to 1.8–2.0 \times on *explosion* and *pulse*, where a single global-density cell size cannot see the local concentration of a clustered distribution. Closed-B sits at 0.99–1.07 \times the per-frame oracle on every 3D scenario — i.e. at the per-frame lower bound within the margin of Section 4.1 — and it matches or beats Closed-A throughout. Compared directly against the static oracle, which shares its timing primitive, Closed-B is within about four percent everywhere and roughly ten percent ahead on *pulse*. The blind search reaches similar ratios but at a recurring cost of milliseconds per frame — comparable to, or larger than, the detection work it is choosing for — whereas Closed-B’s overhead is around $90 \mu\text{s}$.

The 2D results tell the same story in milder form. Ericson is only 1.2–3.1 \times the oracle at $N = 50\text{K}$: in two dimensions the cell count grows as ℓ^{-2} rather than ℓ^{-3} , so the diameter cell is far less punishing than in 3D. The density heuristic again fails on the structured scenarios — *stream* 2.3 \times , *multicluster* 2.1 \times , *pulse* 1.7 \times . Closed-B holds 0.99–1.07 \times the per-frame oracle across all eight scenarios. On *funnel* and *pulse*, the two scenarios with measurable headroom (Section 4.3), Closed-B comes in *below* the static oracle — at 0.92 \times and 0.94 \times — capturing that headroom by re-tuning every frame; on the other six it matches the static oracle to within 2%. Mode B matches or slightly beats Mode A on all but *pulse*, the breathing scenario, whose periodic dimension swing is the one mild challenge to the probe’s smoothing.

At $N = 100\text{K}$ the rule is unchanged — Closed-B stays at $\approx 1.0\times$ — while Ericson’s penalty shrinks further, to 1.0–1.6 \times on the five scenarios that pack to that size. This confirms that the diameter default’s cost is density-dependent: it is least harmful precisely when the distribution is dense enough that $2r$ is close to optimal. Closed-B’s overhead grows linearly with N , as expected of an $O(N)$ probe — from tens of microseconds at $N = 50\text{K}$ toward $\sim 150 \mu\text{s}$ at $N = 100\text{K}$.

4.5 The Role of the Correlation Dimension

On the campaign scenarios above the distribution stays moderately space-filling, and there Closed-A and Closed-B differ by at most a few percent. To isolate the contribution of the correlation-dimension term we need distributions of *controlled* D_2 . We therefore construct static point sets of prescribed correlation dimension: a uniform cloud ($D_2 = d$), an embedded curve and a sheet, and self-similar Cantor dusts whose dimension $D_2 = \log k / \log b$ is tuned from d down to 0.5. Table 3 reports, for each, the cost of Mode A ($D_2 := d$) and of Mode B (measured D_2) relative to the oracle, alongside the dimension the runtime estimator reads; Figure 3 plots the two gaps against D_2 .

The result confirms the thesis and shows it to be strongly dimension-dependent. In two dimensions the effect is modest: as D_2 falls from 2 to 0.5, Mode A’s gap drifts from 1.07 \times to about 1.3 \times — a real but small penalty, and not strictly monotone within seed noise — while Mode B never exceeds 1.12 \times . In three dimensions the effect is dramatic and monotone: Mode A’s gap climbs from 1.11 \times at $D_2 = 3$ to 3.5 \times at $D_2 = 0.5$, because the assumption $D_2 = d$ is the more wrong the larger d is. Mode B cuts this sharply — holding near 1.05 \times down to $D_2 \approx 1.5$, then rising only to 1.23 \times at $D_2 = 1$ and 2.0 \times at the extreme $D_2 = 0.5$, roughly halving Mode A’s gap where it is worst. The benefit of measuring D_2 thus grows with the dimensional deficit $d - D_2$.

The estimator column makes the honest reading explicit. The runtime probe does not recover

Table 2: Main comparison at $N = 50\text{K}$: mean per-frame detection time as a multiple of the per-frame oracle (lower is better; 1.0 is the per-frame lower bound). Mean over five seeds; the per-seed standard deviation is ≤ 0.04 for every entry except the 3D Ericson column (≤ 1.03). The last column is the measured per-frame overhead of Mode B. *multicluster* runs at $N = 20\text{K}$, where its four disks saturate the domain.

Scenario	Ericson	Density	Static	Blind-9	Closed-A	Closed-B	oh (μs)
<i>3D, 200³</i>							
stable	28.71	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.03	0.99	88
collapse	27.41	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.00	91
explosion	15.94	1.77	1.03	1.17	1.08	1.07	106
pulse	16.36	2.04	1.17	1.15	1.08	1.05	107
settling	24.71	1.06	1.03	1.07	1.01	0.99	88
<i>2D, 800 × 600</i>							
stable	2.48	1.00	1.03	1.00	1.07	1.02	64
collapse	2.43	1.03	1.02	1.03	1.08	1.02	63
explosion	2.06	1.21	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.00	69
vortex	1.84	1.29	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	76
funnel	2.07	1.19	1.11	1.04	1.09	1.02	67
pulse	1.36	1.74	1.06	1.02	1.01	1.00	68
multicluster	3.11	2.09	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.00	23
stream	1.17	2.27	1.07	1.06	1.08	1.07	18

the asymptotic correlation dimension; it recovers the *operative local scaling exponent* of S at the grid’s working cell size, as anticipated in Section 3.3. For the dilute, high- D_2 configurations this operative exponent lies well below d — the uniform 3D cloud reads 1.69 rather than 3 — because at an occupancy near one the local log–log slope of S has not yet reached its asymptote. This is precisely the quantity Eq. (5) requires, and it explains why Mode B is at or below Mode A even on the uniform distribution: using the measured operative exponent places ℓ better than assuming the textbook d . On the sparsest $D_2 \approx 0.5$ fractals the estimate becomes noisy and clamps to a floor, but even the clamped value is far closer to the operative truth than $D_2 := d$, so Mode B remains the robust choice. In sum, Mode A is an adequate zero-overhead default for ordinary, near-space-filling scenes, while Mode B is the choice that is never worse and, for low-dimensional distributions in three dimensions, decisively better.

5 Comparison with the Literature

With the measurements in hand we can position the rule precisely against the alternatives surveyed in Section 2.

Against the diameter heuristic. The fixed $\ell = 2r$ default of Ericson [2004] and Green [2010] is the baseline the rule most directly improves on. The experiments quantify when that default is safe and when it is not: it is within a small factor of optimal for dense, near-uniform distributions, but costs $1.2\text{--}3.1\times$ the oracle in 2D and $16\text{--}29\times$ in 3D at $N = 50\text{K}$, with the penalty shrinking as the distribution becomes denser. The default is thus not so much wrong as *regime-dependent*, and a fixed choice cannot know which regime a given frame is in. The closed-form rule removes that guesswork: it reads the regime from the measured cell count and occupancy sum and places ℓ accordingly, for the price of a single formula evaluation.

Figure 3: Cost of Mode A ($D_2 := d$) and Mode B (measured D_2) relative to the oracle, versus the controlled correlation dimension D_2 , in 2D and 3D ($N = 8K$, mean \pm std over five seeds; data of Table 3). The dotted line is the oracle; the dashed vertical line marks the space-filling case $D_2 = d$. As D_2 falls, the fixed assumption $D_2 = d$ misplaces ℓ increasingly badly — mildly in 2D, sharply in 3D — whereas measuring D_2 keeps Mode B close to the oracle throughout.

Against probe-based search. The Blind-9 baseline stands in for the runtime search used by adaptive schemes that try several candidate cell sizes and keep the cheapest. It reaches cell-size quality comparable to the closed-form rule — unsurprisingly, since both aim at the same optimum — but it pays for it: each probe rebuilds the grid for every candidate, costing milliseconds per frame, on the order of or exceeding the broad-phase work it is choosing for. The closed-form rule attains the same quality from one evaluation of Eq. (5) on quantities already computed during the frame, at microsecond cost. In effect it replaces a search with a derivation: where a probe samples the cost curve, the rule uses its shape.

Against analytical cell-sizing. The closest prior work sizes grid cells analytically. Sigurgeirsson et al. [2001] derive scaling laws for the parameters of a cell-based collision algorithm under statistical assumptions on the particle field; Krijgsman et al. [2014] give an analytical recipe for the cell sizes of a *hierarchical* grid keyed to the particle-radius distribution; Rydquist and Esmaily [2020] give an optimal $O(N)$ localisation-and-collision scheme for unstructured grids. We do not claim to be the first to choose a cell size from a model. The contribution here is more specific: the governing quantity is the *spatial* structure of the cloud, captured by its correlation dimension D_2 , rather than the size distribution or a field model; the result is a closed form in quantities measured live, rather than a recipe applied once ahead of time; and it is cheap enough to re-evaluate every frame. The dimension ablation makes the point concretely — the implicit space-filling assumption $D_2 = d$ behind any single static analytic cell size costs up to $3.5\times$ in 3D on low-dimensional distributions, exactly the gap a distribution-aware runtime rule closes.

Spatial hashing and the correlation dimension. Spatial hashing [Teschner et al., 2003, Ihmsen et al., 2011] and grid hierarchies [Eitz and Gu, 2007] address a different axis — variation in object *size* — and are orthogonal to the single-scale, distribution-dependent question studied here;

Table 3: Correlation-dimension ablation on static point sets of controlled D_2 ($N = 8K$, mean \pm std over five seeds). The column “est. D_2 ” is the operative local exponent read by the runtime probe. As D_2 falls below d , Mode A ($D_2 := d$) degrades — mildly in 2D, sharply in 3D — while Mode B (measured D_2) stays close to the oracle. Costs are relative to the oracle.

Configuration	D_2	est. D_2	Mode-A	Mode-B
<i>2D</i>				
uniform	2.00	1.08 ± 0.01	1.07 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.02
Cantor b3k6	1.63	1.14 ± 0.02	1.10 ± 0.02	1.02 ± 0.01
Cantor b3k4	1.26	1.03 ± 0.01	1.15 ± 0.02	1.02 ± 0.01
Cantor b3k3	1.00	0.96 ± 0.00	1.19 ± 0.07	1.07 ± 0.06
curve	1.00	0.97 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.05
Cantor b3k2	0.63	0.66 ± 0.00	1.14 ± 0.07	1.11 ± 0.03
Cantor b9k3	0.50	0.32 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.11	1.12 ± 0.13
<i>3D</i>				
uniform	3.00	1.69 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.01
Cantor b3k9	2.00	1.83 ± 0.03	1.23 ± 0.13	1.05 ± 0.10
sheet	2.00	1.77 ± 0.06	1.22 ± 0.04	1.05 ± 0.04
Cantor b3k5	1.47	1.20 ± 0.02	1.38 ± 0.03	1.08 ± 0.04
Cantor b3k3	1.00	0.99 ± 0.00	2.02 ± 0.11	1.23 ± 0.07
Cantor b3k2	0.63	0.60 ± 0.02	3.22 ± 0.05	1.60 ± 0.13
Cantor b4k2	0.50	0.32 ± 0.01	3.54 ± 0.01	2.00 ± 0.22

the balance principle of Eq. (6) could in principle inform their per-level cell sizes. Finally, the correlation dimension itself [Grassberger and Procaccia, 1983, Hentschel and Procaccia, 1983] has, to our knowledge, not previously been tied to the performance of a spatial data structure. The experiments support that connection as an operative one rather than a mere analogy: the runtime probe recovers the local scaling exponent the cost actually responds to, and using it (Mode B) tracks the oracle across the whole dimension range.

6 Limitations

The rule is deliberately narrow, and several boundaries of its scope should be stated plainly.

Scope of the model. The cost model, the occupancy sum $S = \sum_i n_i^2$, and the $\ell \geq 2r$ clamp all assume *equal-radius* particles and a single uniform grid. Polydisperse systems, in which radii vary widely, are exactly the case a hierarchical grid addresses [Krijgsman et al., 2014], and lie outside the scope of this rule. The measurements come from a single-threaded CPU implementation; the coefficients a and b are hardware- and implementation-specific, and a parallel or GPU build would shift both their values and the per-cell-versus-pair-test balance. The structural form of Eq. (1) and the closed form of Eq. (5) should carry over to such settings with re-calibrated coefficients, but we do not claim the specific numbers transfer.

The size of the prize. We have been explicit (Sections 4.3 and 4.4) that per-frame re-selection of ℓ beats the best single fixed ℓ by only a few percent on most scenarios, with filament-forming *funnel* the one clear exception. A practitioner who can afford an offline sweep for a largely static scene will find a well-chosen fixed grid nearly as fast. The value of the rule is therefore not a large speed-up over a tuned fixed grid; it is that it reaches that performance *automatically*, with no sweep

and no tuning, and stays robust when the distribution — or the dimension — is one for which the fixed heuristics are far from optimal.

The dimension estimate. The runtime probe measures the operative local scaling exponent of S , not the asymptotic correlation dimension; the two differ for dilute, high- D_2 distributions, and the estimate becomes noisy and saturates against its floor on the sparsest low-dimensional fractals (Table 3). Mode B remains robust there — a clamped estimate still places ℓ better than assuming $D_2 = d$ — but the estimated value should not be read as a reliable measurement of the cloud’s dimension at those extremes. Relatedly, the linear cost model is an approximation: on the most violently dynamic scenarios its fit drops to $R^2 \approx 0.88\text{--}0.93$ as cache and bandwidth effects make the densest frames super-linear. The rule tolerates this because only the ratio a/b enters ℓ^* , but the model is not exact.

Scale and motion. The 3D experiments reach $N = 50\text{K}$; at larger 3D sizes and on the most extreme low-dimensional configurations the broad-phase candidate buffer is exhausted, so we report the largest tractable sizes rather than extrapolating past them. And the convergence result (Section 3) assumes a static distribution: under motion the rule carries a one-frame tracking lag, since an update can only target where the optimum was last measured. For the smoothly evolving scenarios studied here that lag is immaterial, but a distribution that reorganises faster than once per frame would not be tracked.

7 Conclusion

We have shown that the optimal cell size of a uniform grid for broad-phase collision detection admits a closed form. Writing the per-frame cost as a linear function of the cell count M and the sum of squared cell occupancies S , recognising S as a discrete Rényi-2 collision quantity, and using that the scaling of S with cell size is governed by the correlation dimension D_2 of the particle cloud, the cost-minimising cell size follows in a single expression — Eq. (5) — in two runtime-measurable cost coefficients and D_2 . The optimum has a clean reading as a balance principle: the cost-optimal grid equates the per-cell and pair-test costs, each weighted by how fast it scales with ℓ . The rule is evaluated once per frame from quantities the grid build already produces, costs microseconds, and needs no tuning.

The experiments support both the model and the rule, in a deliberately honest framing. The linear cost model holds with $R^2 \geq 0.99$ on most scenarios. Per-frame adaptation does not substantially beat a well-chosen fixed cell size — that headroom is small — but the rule reaches the performance of the best fixed ℓ automatically, matching it to within a few percent across eight 2D and five 3D scenarios, and matching an expensive probe-based search at a fraction of its overhead. Where it matters most is on low-dimensional distributions: assuming a space-filling cloud, as the diameter default and any single static cell size implicitly do, costs up to $3.5\times$ in three dimensions, and measuring the correlation dimension at runtime removes most of that penalty.

The correlation dimension, a tool from the analysis of dynamical systems, thus turns out to govern a concrete data-structure performance question. Several directions follow naturally: extending the cost model to polydisperse particles, carrying the closed form to parallel and GPU implementations with re-calibrated coefficients, and using the balance principle to set the per-level cell sizes of hierarchical grids. An open-source implementation and the full experimental harness accompany the paper.

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